

The Conscious Desire Depend on Man Shown by Main Characters in *Little Women's* Novel: The Overview of Cinderella Complex Disorder in Literature

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Abstract:- This study aims to describe the conscious desire depend on man shown by the main characters in Little Women's novel: the overview of Cinderella Complex disorder in literature. The research used the descriptive qualitative method, psychoanalysis theory of Sigmund Freud. This research data is collected from dialogues of the characters in the text Little Women's novel. The research results showed Aunt March and Amy were most influenced by Cinderella Complex. Aunt March consciously realizes her reliance on her husband's wealth, she tried to spread the belief about women would not be able to be succeeded without the help of the man. She also tried to convey the belief that a woman could not grow and prosper without the support of a male. And the second character is Amy. Although in her young state she was not primarily showed the syndrome, but in her older state she was fully aware or conscious of what she was doing could be leading her to be fully dependent on men.

Keywords:- Psychoanalysis, Cinderella Complex, Little Women.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Showalter in Aurelius (2012:15) when viewed from the construction Socio-cultural, gender is not just a difference in male sex with women, but as an analytical concept that can be used to explain. Becker, M. (1999) states patriarchal culture has indirectly provided limits for women, and injustice and inequality have contributed to the closeness of women's identities with women's dependence on men. Miller, J. B. (2012) posed the question of how women develop in her 1976 book, *Toward a New Psychology of Women*. Until then, traditional theories of psychology described the development as a climb from childlike dependence to mature independence. A person's goal was to become a self-sufficient, clearly differentiated, autonomous self. A person would spend her life separating and individuating until he or she reached maturity, at which point the person was equipped for intimacy. Chodoff, (1966) states that Freud was beginning to formulate his controversial theories on infantile sexuality and dream interpretation, both of which are central to psychoanalytic theory. Shevrin, H. (1996) Psychoanalysis provides the fundamental idea that all conscious thought and action is an unconscious process which is summarized in the

phrase the unconscious mind. Behavior in everyday life is conscious behavior in the unconscious. Kohrman, et. al (1971) Repression of the unconscious will be manifested in unconscious behavior such as tongue sprains, misbehavior, fantasies, and dreams. Psychological pressures can be in the form of hopes, dreams, ideas, desires, feelings of pleasure or displeasure, traumatic experiences, neurotic anxiety (anxiety), fear (phobia), both in personal life and in social life.

According to Dowling (1982: 4) Since women are very young, they avoid all things that would frighten them, they prefer to do activities that make them feel comfortable and protected. Women are not free. Women who oppose being dominated by others, in general, are scared of taking charge of their own lives. They are apprehensive about charting their course. Haslam, N. (2016) states women are terrified of movement, exploration, change, and everything unusual or unknown to them, including the most debilitating of all, natural aggressiveness and assertiveness. Traditionally, women are not expected to face their fears and overcome them.

Abrams (1999: 190) states that a novel differs from a short story in terms of the number of pages it contains; a novel might have hundreds of pages, whilst a short story only has a handful. The term "novel" is currently used to describe a wide range of works that all have one thing in common: they are long works of fiction written in prose. The book differs from the short story in that it is a longer narrative and from the work of middle length called the novelette. Like other literary works, a novel includes numerous lessons, especially for young readers. Novel entitled *Little Woman* by American author, Louisa May Alcott (1832-1888). This story of the novel is based on the real-life of the author and her three sisters. The researcher hopes that by conducting this study, she will be able to provide more knowledge and understanding about the psychoanalysis and Cinderella Complex in literature, and thus help people avoid it as early as possible.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Puspitasari (2019) states that Freud's hypothesis on human conduct keeps on having a solid impact in the field of psychoanalytic treatment and writing examination. His hypothesis depends on rehashing examples of broken human

conduct that he saw while treating patients with intense subject matters for a long time. Bain (1859) said the oblivious psyche/ unconscious mind impacts human conduct since it houses impressions of dread, memory, delight, struggle, and agony, in addition to other things. Freud in Niaz et al. (2019) states the memories that are stored in the unconscious are mostly from the past, particularly from childhood, while Jung accepts that these recollections are from the past as well as have future and current ramifications. He also believes that these memories are particular to the individual and are linked to his or her ancestors. Spiro, (2017) said the sentiments of attachment that a boy has for his mother are referred to as the "Oedipus Complex" by Sigmund Freud. Psychoanalysis is named after the connection between dreams and literature; these conscious and unconscious sensations originate in people's thoughts.

Psychoanalysis, basing his thinking on unconscious processes that shape behavior and all behavioral deviations as a result of unconscious processes. Psychoanalysis does not aim or seek anything except the discovery of the subconscious in mental life (Freud 2002:424). The process of unconsciousness as psychic energy that gets continuous repression without sublimation will cause symptoms that result in neuroses and continue to mental disorders. Segal, H. (1978) For Freud, a dream is a (hidden) fulfillment of a desire (repressed or ignored) or in other words, a dream is a kind of code. The symbols that appear in dreams are symbols of the unconscious being repressed. Hossain (2017: 4) explained that if the psychoanalysis theory applied toward literary works, then the implementation of the theory would focus on one of the following terms, they are the author, where the theory is utilized to study the author, either his life or the relation between the author and the literary work itself; The characters in the story, where the theory is applied to one or more characters, and the psychoanalysis will explain the behaviors and motives of the characters; The audience, where the theory is used on why people enjoy the literary work. The theory is also applied to the work to examine the function of language and symbolism in the work. Psychoanalytic principles impact authors and writers, which are mirrored in characters in the literary work and also in their minds.

Freud (1920) said the "Id," is an innate part of the unconscious that is suppressed by the "superego," our conscious awareness of society's moral values, and the "ego," which does not allow clashes to occur when people are going to participate in our dream life with the help of the "ego" part of their personality. In dreams, there are no social constraints, and the "ego" would assist it in expressing sentiments connected to the "id." In many cases, the wants of the id can be met through a process of late fulfillment. The ego will eventually allow the conduct, but only when the time and place are right. The "superego" educates people's conduct as a teacher beyond the age of five, and repressed sentiments, as well as feelings that makeup people content in dreams, might surface in our dreams at the proper time and place. In people's dreams, they play the roles of director, actor, and interpreter.

Dowling, (1982:86) the first person who introduced Cinderella Complex in her book Cinderella Complex; Woman's Hidden Fear from Independence, describes Cinderella Complex as suppressed attitudes and anxieties, which corresponds to Sigmund Freud's psychoanalytic ideas. Perrault's Cinderella exemplifies how the heroine of the narrative must be "rescued" by a man of royal substance and assisted by external powers to get attention and esteem. Cinderella holds no resentment against her oppressors, the stepsisters, and stepmother; instead, she is courteous and compassionate. A woman is taught through this narrative that to endure such tyranny, she must be patient and good and wait for the day when the reward for such perseverance arrives in the shape of a man. As a result, young women are socialized to be dependent. Its plot is based on the idea that women should be "attractive, courteous, graceful, hardworking, submissive, and docile." Cinderella functions as a patriarchal tool, creating and fostering psychological reliance in women. Not only that, after some time out in the world, even ladies who have graduated from college are affected by this syndrome. They began to be tugged by that old longing for protection, the wish to be protected, as the first pleasure of independence faded and dread rose in its stead. Dowling further stated that the Cinderella concept typically affects adolescent females, stopping them from finishing their schooling and hastening their adolescent years. Women who have already finished higher education are particularly vulnerable to Cinderella mentality. Dowling (1982: 4) also explains that Cinderella Complex arises when a woman has a strong need to be protected and cared for by others, particularly males. Furthermore, Douvan's studies state that females do not influence their journey toward independence until they are eighteen or older (1982: 101).

A novel just like other literary works, includes numerous lessons, especially for young readers. This Cinderella Complex syndrome is also revealed in a novel entitled *Little Woman*. This story of the novel is based on the real-life of the author and her three sisters. In the novel, Jo March remembers her life from the past to the present, then tells the story of the March sisters who were determined to live their lives according to their respective choices. The researcher is highly interested to discuss Cinderella Complex syndrome which is still less known by women in general. As a woman, the researcher believes that this Cinderella Complex developed in her environment without the victims' knowledge. Thus, the researcher hopes that by conducting this study, she will be able to provide more knowledge and understanding about the syndrome, and thus help people avoid it as early as possible, because, according to Dowling (1982: 64), Cinderella Complex is used to target girls as young as sixteen or seventeen, preventing them from attending college and forcing them into early marriages. Since the current research is about Cinderella Complex syndrome which has a lot of relation about a thought or mental state of women that has a relationship with psychology that is why the researcher thinks that the psychoanalysis approach is the most suitable approach method for the research.

III. METHODOLOGY

Purwaningsih, et al.,(2020) noted that qualitative study is conducted naturally using descriptive data. It means that in the identification of the data descriptive, the qualitative study was used to determine the methodology of this research. To identify literary works as psychology and literature, data was gathered. The descriptive qualitative method was used in this research because this research focuses on the Cinderella Complex syndrome of the female characters in Louisa May Alcott's Little Women novel, and this research has nothing to do with numbering or calculation. That is why a qualitative method is the best method for the research the data resource of this research is the Little Women novel written by Louisa May Alcott. It has two volumes, the first volume was published in 1868, and the second volume was published in 1869. The total pages of both volumes are 664. The psychoanalysis was used to analyze the behavior and thoughts of the female characters in Louisa May Alcott's Little Women, and Cinderella Complex was used as the indicator to find Cinderella Complex represented by female characters in Louisa May Alcott's Little Women. The data was found in the dialogues and monologues of the female characters.

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

a. Aunt March

Data 1

- Aunt March : "Not yet. I've something to say to you, and I must free my mind at once. Tell me, do you mean to marry this Cook? If you do, not one penny of my money ever goes to you. Remember that, and be a sensible girl"
- Meg : "I shall marry whom I please, Aunt March, and you can leave your money to anyone you like,"
- Aunt March : "Highty-tighty! Is that the way you take my advice, Miss? You'll be sorry for its by-and-by when you've tried love in a cottage and found it a failure"
- Meg : "It can't be a worse one than some people find in big houses,"
- Aunt March : "Now, Meg, my dear, be reasonable and take my advice. I mean it kindly and don't want you to spoil your whole life by making a mistake at the beginning. You ought to marry well and help your family. It's your duty to make a rich match and it ought to be impressed upon you" (Alcott, 1868: 322-323).

Meg and Aunt March were debating what sort of men Meg should marry in the context of the dialog above. Aunt March, based on the speech, was the character that displayed Cinderella Complex. In this dialog, Aunt March consciously warned Meg to rethink whether the decision she made was right or wrong because she wanted to marry a cook who did not meet the standards of economic adequacy according to

Aunt March's wishes. From these data, it shows that Aunt March is very consciously dependent on men.

Data 2

- Aunt March : "This Rook is poor and hasn't got any rich relations, has he?"
- Meg : "No, but he has many warm friends."
- Aunt March : "You can't live on friends, try it and see how cool they'll grow. He hasn't any business, has he?"
- Meg : "Not yet. Mr. Laurence is going to help him"
- Aunt March : "That won't last long. James Laurence is a crotchety old fellow and not to be depended on. So, you intend to marry a man without money, position, or business, and go on working harder than you do now when you might be comfortable all your days by minding me and doing better? I thought you had more sense, Meg" (Alcott, 1868: 323)

Meg and Aunt March were debating about what sort of men Meg should marry in the context of the abovedialogue. According to the conversation, the characters who demonstrated Cinderella Complex were Meg and Aunt March. Meg was insisted on marrying the man she chose and defending him by expressing how she and her husband would still rely on other people, meanwhile Aunt March was still on her point.

Meg in this conversation tried to defend her future husband from the argument of Aunt March by expressing her reliance not only on her husband but also on being dependent on others. Aunt March on other hand, was quite contrary against Meg, where she argued that relying on others was not a very wise thing to do, however, she kept insisting Meg marry a wealthy man, so Meg would only rely on her husband.

Data 3

- Aunt March : "I wish you well, my dear, I heartily wish you well, but I think you'll be sorry for it, you've got a treasure, young man, see that you deserve it" (Alcott, 1868: 355)

Aunt March, who was present at Meg's wedding, is the focus of the monologue above. Aunt March was the figure who had Cinderella Complex, as seen by the speech. Even though that Aunt March was finally yielded to Meg's choice to marry the man she chose, Aunt March was still showing her thought of marrying a wealthy man. Aunt March's statement above indicated an aspect of Cinderella Complex. Similar to the previous data where Aunt March insisted on making her niece marry a wealthy man, it also occurred in this data. She thought that Meg would regret her decision later by marrying a non-wealthy man.

Practically she was not showing Cinderella Complex, it was more on pushing the idea of Cinderella Complex to others, in this case, to her niece. Aunt March, herself was

described as an old widow who lived in wealth and was only accompanied by her servants and pets. Quite different from some old characters in most narratives which are described as having wisdom, Aunt March was depicted with more stubbornness and temper. Her fortune which presumably came from her late husband was the main cause of her having the idea of relying upon one man, or in her words “marry well” was the only way for a woman to be successful and happy in her life. She tried to put this idea on her niece, Meg. As has been mentioned earlier, Aunt March who had a great fortune and was highly dependent on it caused her to make a self-concept where she thought that without a rich man or a rich husband, a woman could never be happy and prosperous. Thus, even she was not practicing Cinderella Complex and more on spreading the ideas of it, Aunt March was still considered as hugely impact with Cinderella Complex. The worst part about Aunt March having the condition was that she was well aware of her Cinderella Complex notions and attempted to transmit them purposefully to others. So, it can be concluded that she very consciously has dependent her life on men.

b. Amy
Data 4

- Amy : “It isn’t a mere pleasure trip to me, girls, it will decide my career, for if I have any genius, I shall find it out in Rome, and will do something to prove it.”
- Jo : “Suppose you haven’t?”
- Amy : “Then I shall come home and teach drawing for my living.”
- Jo : “No, you won’t. You hate hard work, and you’ll marry some rich man, and come home to sit in the lap of luxury all your days,” (Alcott, 1868: 433).

The discussion above takes place in the context of Jo and Amy who were arguing about Amy being chosen by her Aunt to visit Rome. Amy was the character who demonstrated Cinderella Complex, as seen by the conversation. Amy was described by Jo as a person who is fond of wealth and being luxurious. Amy’s description by Jo indicated it. In the dialogue above, Amy was describing what she wanted to do during her travel. What Amy mentioned was sounded like an act of independence, however, Jo had another description about her. she described her sister who would not do what she said, and instead relied on the man to become wealthy. The things that Jo was explained cannot be proved based on the current chapter on the novel yet, but deeper in the novel, it would be proofed eventually in another data. The way Jo described Amy was depicting Amy who hated to work but demand prosperity and luxury, which is considered immature behavior.

Data 5:

- Amy : “Now I know Mother will shake her head, and the girls say, ‘Oh, the mercenary little wretch!’, but I’ve made up my mind, and if Fred asks me, I shall accept him, though I’m not madly in love. I

like him, and we get on comfortably together. He is handsome, young, clever enough, and very rich—ever so much richer than the Laurences. I don’t think his family would object, and I should be very happy, for they are all kind, well-bred, generous people, and they like me. Fred, as the eldest twin, will have the estate, I suppose, and such a splendid one it is! A city house in a fashionable street, not so showy as our big houses, but twice as comfortable and full of solid luxuries, such as English people believe in. I like it, for it’s genuine. I’ve seen the plate, the family jewels, the old servants, and pictures of the country place, with its park, great house, lovely grounds, and fine horses. Oh, it would be all I should ask! And I’d rather have it than any title such as girls snap up so readily, and find nothing behind. I may be mercenary, but I hate poverty and don’t mean to bear it a minute longer than I can help. One of us must marry well. Meg didn’t, Jo won’t, Beth can’t yet, so I shall, and make everything okay all round. I wouldn’t marry a man I hated or despised. You may be sure of that, and though Fred is not my model hero, he does very well, and in time I should get fond enough of him if he was very fond of me, and let me do just as I liked” (Alcott, 1868: 445).

The context of the preceding monologue is a part of Amy’s letter to her family when she was overseas. From what can be seen from the dialogue, the character that showed Cinderella Complex was Amy. Amy described her intention of marrying a wealthy man. In the dialogue above, Amy was describing her intention to marry a man, at first, she only explained about the man status who was well breed, wealthy, etc., without showing any type of Cinderella Complex. However, near the end of her letter, she mentioned her reason and stated that one of the siblings should marry well, or in the other words, marry a wealthy man. As the story progressed, Amy had a storyline in which she was chosen as a companion by Aunt March. From that event, it can be assumed that Amy was taken care of by her Aunt to become a noblewoman with a lady-like personality. Even though that it was not mentioned in the novel, but the way Amy mentioned why she should marry a wealthy man supported the assumption.

Amy barely had any personal maturity and always considered her appearance as the most important to her, not only that, since her family had a service that always helped her chores which made her become a little bit independent, at least when she was younger. Then, in her older state of age, she started to produce a negative about herself, not only on how insignificant her talent was according to her, but the worse part was she thought about becoming a gold digger (a person whose romantic pursuit of, relationship with, or marriage to a wealthy person or solely motivated by a desire for money). For these reasons, Amy was considered on having Cinderella Complex and was majorly impacted by it. Although in her young state she was not primarily showed the syndrome, but in her older state she was fully aware or

conscious of what she was doing could be leading to herself being fully dependent on men.

V. CONCLUSION

Aunt March and Amy are used to represent the conscious desire depend on man shown by the main characters in *Little Women's* novel as the overview of Cinderella Complex disorder in literature. The extent to which a character is influenced by Cinderella Complex varies depending on how Cinderella Complex influences their behavior and thoughts, specifically consciousness. Aunt March was described as an old widow who lived in wealth and was only accompanied by her servants and pets. Quite different from some old characters in most narratives which are described as having wisdom, Aunt March was depicted with more stubbornness and temper. Her fortune which presumably came from her late husband was the main cause of her having the idea of relying on one man, or in her words "marry well" was the only way for a woman to be successful and happy in her life. She tried to put this idea on her niece, Meg. Not only consciously realize her reliance on her husband's wealth, but she was also tried to spread the belief about women would not be able to be succeeded without the help of men. Thus, even she was not practicing Cinderella Complex and more on spreading the ideas of it, Aunt March was still considered as hugely impact with Cinderella Complex. The worst part about Aunt March having the condition was that she was well aware of her Cinderella Complex notions and attempted to transmit them purposefully to others. Amy was suffered even more from Cinderella Complex syndrome because she stated about her reliance on men consciously. She literally mentioned her desire to marry a wealthy man in order to gain success and prosperity. The character Amy most dominated relying on men.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Abrams, M. H. (1999). *A Glossary of Literary terms* (7th ed.). Boston: Heinle&Heinle.
- [2.] Alcott, L.M., (1868). *Little Women*. England: Penguin Books Ltd.
- [3.] Arafah, B., Abbas, H., & Hikmah, N. (2021). Saving the Environment: Environmental Lessons in Colin Thiele's February Dragon. *Journal of Language and Research*, 12 (6), 935-941.
- [4.] Aurelius, E. H. (2012). Theoretical foundation. *Women's Language: An Analysis of Style and Expression in Letters Before 1800*. Sweden: Nordic Academic Press.
- [5.] Bain, A. (1859). *The Emotions and The Will*. London: John W. Parker and Son.
- [6.] Baker, K. K. (2007). Bionormativity and the Construction of Parenthood. *Ga. L. Rev.*, 42, 649.
- [7.] Becker, M. (1999). Patriarchy and inequality: Towards substantive feminism. *U. Chi. Legal F.*, 21
- [8.] Calhoun, J. F., & Acocella, J. R. (1990). *Psychology of Adjustment and Human Relationship*. New York: Mc Graw Hill, Inc.
- [9.] Chaplin, J. P. (1985). *Dictionary of Psychology*. New York: Bantam Doubleday Dell Publishing Group.
- [10.] Chodoff, P. (1966). A critique of Freud's theory of infantile sexuality. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 123(5), 507-518.
- [11.] Dowling, C. (1982). *The Cinderella Complex, Women's Hidden Fear of Independence*. New York: Pocket Books.
- [12.] Fatimah, E., & Istiani, I. (2020). Cinderella Syndrome of Working Women in Cyber Literature. *E-Structural (English Studies on Translation, Culture, Literature, and Linguistics)*, 3(02), 131-144.
- [13.] Freud, S. (1920). *A general introduction to psychoanalysis*. New York: Boni and Liveright.
- [14.] Hasanah, U., Arafah, B., & Abbas, H. (2021). The Values of Character Education in Pullman's *The Golden Compass*. *Multicultural Education*, 7(1), 142-148.
- [15.] Haslam, N. (2016). Concept creep: Psychology's expanding concepts of harm and pathology. *Psychological Inquiry*, 27(1), 1-17.
- [16.] Holland, N. N. (1999). The story of a Psychoanalytic Critic. *American Imago*, 56(3), 245-259.
- [17.] Hossain, M. (2017). Psychoanalytic theory used in English literature: A descriptive study. *Global Journal of Human-Social Science: Linguistics & Education*, 17(1), 41-46.
- [18.] Irmawati, I., Arafah, B., & Abbas, H. (2020). The Lesson Life of Santiago As Main Character in Coelho's *The Alchemist*. *Jurnal Ilmu Budaya*, 8(1), 32-36.
- [19.] Kitzinger, C., & Wilkinson, S. (1995). Transitions from heterosexuality to lesbianism: The discursive production of lesbian identities. *Developmental Psychology*, 31(1), 95-104.
- [20.] Kohrman, R., Fineberg, H. H., Gelman, R. L., & Weiss, S. (1971). Technique of child analysis: Problems of countertransference. *International Journal of Psycho-Analysis*, 52, 487-497.
- [21.] Miller, J. B. (2012). *Toward a new psychology of women*. Boston: Beacon Press.
- [22.] Niaz, A., Stanikzai, S. M., & Sahibzada, J. (2019). Review of Freud's psychoanalysis approach to literary studies. *American International Journal of Social Science Research*, 4(2), 35-44.
- [23.] Ogden, T. (1997). Reverie and metaphor: Some thoughts on how I work as a psychoanalyst. *International Journal of Psycho-Analysis*, 78, 719-732.
- [24.] Purwaningsih, Arafah, B., & Abbas, Herawary. (2019). An ambition of Infidelity "Emma Bovary" as Wife: Sexuality Problems. *Medical Clinica Practica*, 3 (S1):100108, 1-3.
- [25.] Purwaningsih, Y. R., Arafah, B., Abbas, H., & Arafah, A. N. B. (2020). Psychological Disorder of Emma Bovary as a Wife toward Sexuality Dissatisfaction in Gustave Flaubert *Madame Bovary*. *Journal of Talent Development and Excellence*, 12(3s), 1382-1389.
- [26.] Puspitasari, R. (2019). *A Cinderella Complex Issue in Female Protagonists of Bronte's Jane Eyre and Meyer's Twilight: A Psychoanalytic Study* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Universitas Sanata Dharma Yogyakarta.

- [27.] Schneiders, A. A. (1964). *Personal adjustment and mental health*. New York: Rinehart and Winston.
- [28.] Segal, H. (1978). On symbolism. *International Journal of Psycho-Analysis*, 59, 315-319.
- [29.] Shevrin, H. (Ed.). (1996). *Conscious and unconscious processes: Psychodynamic, cognitive, and neurophysiological convergences*. New York: Guilford Press.
- [30.] Spiro, M. E. (2017). *Oedipus in the Trobriands*. New York: Routledge.
- [31.] Sunardi., Akil., M., Arafah, B., &Salija, K. (2018). Looking at the Shared Conception of Teaching Literature in an Indonesian ELT Setting. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 9 (2), 316-327.

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